

MOON AND PLANETS

Polarimetric study of main belt and near-Earth asteroids

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This work briefly presents the results of polarimetric observations of main belt and near-Earth asteroids (NEAs) carried out at the telescopes of the Crimean Astrophysical Observatory and the "Terskol Peak" Observatory. Phase-polarization curves were constructed for 32 NEAs, with such data being obtained for the first time for most of these objects. This allowed for a more precise determination of the parameters of the polarization curves at large phase angles. For the Main Belt asteroids, a comparison was made between the morphological phase curves of the degree of polarization and the most common spectral classifications (Tholen, SMASSII, Mahlke). It was established that the phase-dependencies of the degree of polarization of asteroids show the least scatter when compared with the Mahlke classification, while the phase curves of the degree of polarization of asteroids demonstrate significant deviations with the Tholen and SMASSII classifications. The results confirm the high significance of polarimetry as an independent tool for diagnosing the composition and structure of asteroid surfaces.

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1. INTRODUCTION

Asteroids are small bodies of the Solar System, ranging in size from meters to hundreds of kilometers. Most are located in the main belt (MB), but many also approach Earth (NEAs). These objects are considered "time capsules" preserving primordial material from the protoplanetary nebula [1].

Studying asteroids is essential both for understanding Solar System evolution and for applied goals. NEAs may pose impact threats [2] and serve as potential sources of minerals and volatiles. Space missions like NEAR Shoemaker, Hayabusa, Hayabusa2, and OSIRIS-REx have revealed unprecedented details about asteroid surface properties [3]-[5].

Given the large number of known asteroids (>1.4 million), remote sensing methods are key. Spectrophotometry and photometry are widely used to obtain reflectance spectra and estimate albedo, color indices, rotation, and taxonomy. Another promising technique is polarimetry, which measures the linear polarization of reflected light. It provides constraints on albedo, surface roughness, and regolith properties. Combined with spectroscopy and photometry, polarimetry significantly enhances our understanding of asteroid surfaces.

2. POLARIMETRIC OBSERVATIONS OF ASTEROIDS

Polarimetry measures the linear polarization P_r of sunlight scattered by atmosphereless bodies. This value depends on the phase angle α , wavelength λ , and surface properties. The most informative diagnostic is the phase-polarization dependence $P(\alpha)$, whose shape and parameters (e.g., P_{\min} , α_{inv} , h) reflect particle size, albedo, heterogeneity, and space weathering.

Figure 1: Typical phase-polarization curve for atmosphereless Solar System bodies and its main parameters: P_{\min} , α_{\min} , α_{inv} , h , P_{\max} , α_{\max} .

For main belt asteroids (typically observed at $\alpha < 30^\circ$), the following empirical approximation is used [6]:

$$P_r(\alpha) = A \left(e^{-\alpha/B} - 1 \right) + C\alpha. \quad (1)$$

For NEAs, which can be observed at larger phase

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angles, a more general model applies [7]:

$$P_r(\alpha) = A \sin^B \alpha \cdot \cos^C \left(\frac{\alpha}{2} \right) \sin(\alpha - \alpha_{\text{inv}}). \quad (2)$$

Here, α is the phase angle; α_{inv} is the inversion angle (the angle where polarization changes sign); and A, B, C are empirical parameters fitted to observational data.

Polarimetric parameters are empirically linked to geometric albedo [8]. Combined with absolute magnitude H_v , they allow diameter estimates [9]. Thus, phase-polarization curves serve as a powerful diagnostic, especially when used alongside spectroscopy and photometry.

3. RESULTS OF NEA POLARIMETRY: NEW DATA AND FEATURES OF SOME OBJECTS

Since 2019, a program of observations of near-Earth asteroids (NEAs) has been implemented at the Crimean Astrophysical Observatory and at the "Terkol Peak" Observatory (INASAN) using two-channel aperture photoelectric polarimeters [10]. Thanks to the use of a fast modulation method with synchronous detection, a high measurement accuracy is achieved (from $\sim 0.02\%$ for objects of $\sim 7^m$ to $\sim 0.5\%$ for objects of $\sim 17^m$ in the V and R filters).

During the period 2019–2025, polarimetric curves were obtained for 32 NEAs, with 29 of these objects being observed for the first time. The observations cover a wide range of phase angles – up to 130° , which is fundamentally impossible for main belt bodies. This allows for the refinement of the parameters of the phase-polarization curves for different spectral classes – S, C, and E, and to use these data to estimate the albedo, diameter, and physical nature of the objects [11].

Of particular interest are objects with extreme characteristics. For example, NEA 25330 (1999 KV4) showed a record degree of polarization – 38.5% at a phase angle of 75.7° , close to the high degree of polarization of comet C/1995 O1 (Hale–Bopp) (Fig. 2). This may indicate sublimation-dust activity of the studied NEA.

The pair of asteroids 52768 and 159402, which have similar orbital and polarimetric parameters, probably represent fragments of a common parent body [12]

4. POLARIMETRIC CHARACTERISTICS OF MAIN BELT ASTEROIDS IN THE CONTEXT OF MODERN CLASSIFICATIONS

While polarimetric observations of NEAs are still in the data accumulation phase by the scientific community, there is already sufficient information about main belt asteroids for statistical analysis. Most often, a comparison is made between the degree of polarization as a function of the phase angle and the spectral class of the asteroid.

Figure 2: Phase dependence of polarization of NEA 25330 (1999 KV4) in the V and R filters and of comet C/1995 O1 (Hale–Bopp).

Currently, three prevalent asteroid classifications are in use: Tholen [13], SMASSII (Small Main-belt Asteroid Spectroscopic Survey - vers.II) [14], and Mahlke [15].

The Tholen system is based on broadband photometry and albedo, dividing asteroids into main classes (C, S, M, E) that differ by reflectance spectra and average albedo. SMASSII relies on high-resolution spectra in the $0.4\text{--}1.0 \mu\text{m}$ range, omits albedo, and splits large groups into subclasses (e.g., Sq, Sr), while merging E, M, and P into a general X-type. Mahlke combines spectral features with albedo, but uses fewer subclasses.

These differences may lead to inconsistent classification of individual objects. For instance, asteroid 339 Dorothea is classified as S-, K-, and B-type in the Tholen, SMASSII, and Mahlke schemes, respectively. This highlights the need for additional constraints, such as polarimetric data.

We analyzed phase-polarization dependencies for 154 main belt asteroids (based on APDB (Asteroid Polarimetric Database) and recent publications), focusing on C, S, and M groups. Average curves were fitted using the Muinonen model [6], and characteristic uncertainty corridors of $\pm 5\sigma$ were determined. Asteroids with deviations exceeding $\pm 10\sigma$ from the mean curve are marked in Figs. 3a–3c in red. A summary of the comparison by group is provided below.

4.1. C-complex

The SMASSII classification shows good correspondence, thanks to the introduction of subclasses Ch, Cgh, etc., thereby grouping objects with very similar properties within one group. The Tholen classification shows a large scatter, while the Mahlke classification provides stable results with the exception of individual outliers (Fig. 3a).

tween two classifications – Tholen and Mahlke. A significant scatter of polarization values among M-class asteroids is reflected, for example, in the work of [16], which is visible in Fig.3c. Moreover, for the Mahlke classification, several groups of polarimetrically similar asteroids can be distinguished (above and below the approximating curve). This class requires additional observations and study, and the need to involve polarimetric data is evident.

4.4. Total

Polarimetric comparison with the three taxonomies shows: (i) Tholen (photometry+albedo) covers major types but shows high intra-class scatter in $P(\alpha)$; (ii) SMASSII (spectra) often aligns where subclassing is rich, but ignores albedo and merges E/M/P into X, reducing separability; (iii) Mahlke (spectra+albedo) provides the most consistent grouping for C and S, while M-types still display broad scatter and possible subgroups. Thus, polarimetry offers an independent criterion for identifying misclassified asteroids (see Figs. 3a–3c) and refining class boundaries; further observations of M-types are especially important.

5. CONCLUSION

Polarimetric studies continue to demonstrate high potential for studying the physical properties of asteroids, both in the main belt and those near-Earth. Ob-

servations at the Crimean Astrophysical Observatory and the "Terskol Peak" Observatory have yielded new phase-polarization curves for over 30 NEAs, substantially enriching the database, especially at large phase angles.

A comparison of the polarimetric data of main belt asteroids with common spectral classifications (Tholen, SMASSII, Mahlke) has shown that each has its strengths and limitations. While Tholen suffers from significant scatter within broad classes and SMASSII from excessive detail, the new Mahlke system demonstrates stability and internal consistency, although it also requires clarification.

Overall, polarimetry serves as a valuable independent method for verifying and improving asteroid taxonomy. Combined with photometry and spectroscopy, it enhances our understanding of the composition, structure, and evolution of small Solar System bodies.

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CONFLICT OF INTEREST

The authors of this work declare that they have no conflicts of interest.

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